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EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL MEDIA ON INDIGENOUS CULTURE IN KAZAKHSTAN

Abstract: The rapid advancement of digital technology has brought about a fundamental shift in how cultural heritage is perceived and disseminated. This paper investigates the transformative impact of digital media on indigenous culture in Kazakhstan and its implications for global communication. Through an analysis of Kazakhstan's cultural landscape and digital media trends, we explore the dynamic influence of various digital platforms, spanning social media, online news, entertainment, arts, education, and training. Additionally, we examine how digital media platforms shape the representation of Kazakhstani indigenous culture, including language, cultural symbols, and core values. This study illuminates the evolving relationship between digital technology and cultural preservation, highlighting the potential for digital media to enhance the accessibility and interactivity of cultural heritage while fostering cross-cultural understanding on a global scale.

Keywords: Digital Media, Indigenous Culture, Kazakhstan, Cultural Heritage, Global Communication.

Introduction

With the advent of the digital age, the field of media is undergoing profound transformations. Digital media, as one of the key driving forces of this revolution, is leading the dissemination and shaping of culture on a global scale. In this wave, Kazakhstan, as a country in Central Asia, plays a crucial role in shaping and disseminating its local culture through digital media.

In the framework of this study, we will initially examine the cultural context of Kazakhstan and the developmental trends of digital media in the country. Through an analysis of these two pivotal factors, we will uncover the underlying mechanisms by which digital media influences local culture. Subsequently, we will focus on the different types of digital media and their unique roles in cultural shaping, including social media, online news and entertainment platforms, as well as digital art and entertainment content. This will aid us in gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the penetration and shaping of digital media in local culture.

In delving deeper into the exploration of how digital media shapes local culture, we will focus on the expression of language, cultural symbols, and the reflection of indigenous values in digital media. Through analysis of these aspects, we can better comprehend how digital media serves as a medium for cultural shaping and what impact it has on the dissemination of Kazakhstan's indigenous culture.

Literature Review

As the digital landscape continues to evolve, the role of digital media in facilitating the communication and preservation of indigenous cultural heritage becomes increasingly pivotal. Digital media platforms offer unique opportunities for indigenous communities in Kazakhstan to showcase their cultural traditions, beliefs, and practices to a global audience. Cultural representation through digital media in Kazakhstan is a multifaceted topic that has been explored through various lenses in recent research endeavors.

The landscape of digital media in Kazakhstan has been a subject of increasing interest in recent years, reflecting the country's growing integration into the global digital sphere. Brennen and Kress's (2016) study highlights digitalization as a means to restructure societal aspects through the reorganization of digital communication and media infrastructure [1], emphasizing the significant role digitalization plays within the media system. Moreover, the examination of social distance between ethnic groups in Kazakhstan by Kaliev et al. (2024) provided insights into the complexities of intergroup dynamics and the importance of understanding cultural diversity within the country [2]. Zatonskaya (2020) examined the transformations in digital age media within Kazakhstan [3]. By exploring the changing media dynamics influenced by technological advancements, this research contributes to understanding the evolving media landscape in the country. Moreover, Nugumanova et al. (2023) delved into the role of digital media as a factor of information security in Kazakhstan [4]. The authors highlighted how the media landscape in the country has evolved to actively engage citizens in political processes, illustrating the instrumental role of digital platforms in shaping political realities. Furthermore, Kilybayev (2024) explored the development of digital competencies among young teachers in Kazakhstan, emphasizing the profound impact of digital socialization on the new generation [5]. By studying the influence of digital culture on adolescents, this research provides valuable insights into the integration of digital technologies in educational practices within the Kazakh context.

Barlybayeva (2021) explored the interplay between creativity and media culture in modern Kazakhstan [6]. This study sheds light on how digital media platforms are utilized as tools for self-expression and representation in the Kazakh context. Moreover, Temirbayeva et al. (2023) investigated the digital palette of Kazakhstan through the lens of Tengrian internet communities [7]. This study delved into how these groups leverage digital platforms for communication, interaction, and dissemination of their cultural narratives, offering insights into the intersection of traditional cultural practices with digital media technologies. Additionally, the research by Barlybayeva and Mysaeva (2019) touched upon the new social-cultural order and new media in Kazakhstan, emphasizing the balance between technological advancements and cultural preservation [8]. These studies collectively enrich our understanding of cultural representation, identity, and the profound influence of digital media on shaping the socio-cultural landscape of Kazakhstan. As we navigate through this digital era, it

becomes increasingly imperative to recognize and appreciate the intricate interplay between technological advancements and cultural preservation.

In conclusion, the confluence of creativity, information security, cultural preservation, media transformations, and educational advancements underscore the multifaceted evolution of digital media in Kazakhstan. These studies collectively contribute to painting a comprehensive picture of the rise and development of digital media within the country, showcasing its dynamic intersection with various aspects of society and culture.

Discussion

In recent years, with the rapid proliferation of the internet and the advent of the digital age, the digital economy has penetrated into the lives of people in a completely new way. This development not only serves as a driving force in technological innovation but also profoundly impacts people's lifestyles. Particularly in culturally diverse countries like Kazakhstan, the rapid advancement of the digital economy has become a significant transformation in the modes, forms, and promotion methods of indigenous cultural dissemination. Digital media, as a significant product of technological development, has become mainstream in the media industry and plays a crucial role in disseminating indigenous culture. Moreover, digital technologies such as the internet, cloud computing, 5G, artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and virtual reality add new vitality to cultural dissemination. Through digital media, indigenous culture can be spread globally and receive broader recognition. Digital media not only accelerates the speed of indigenous cultural dissemination but also expands its reach, enabling Kazakhstan's culture to engage in deeper exchanges and interactions with people worldwide. Thus, digital information has become an indispensable and highly valuable aspect of Kazakhstan's social development.

Digital media is a form of media based on digital technology and network communication, primarily consisting of digitized information, including various forms of information such as text, images, sounds, and videos recorded, stored, processed, and transmitted in digital format. The emergence and development of digital media have spurred innovation and transformation in the media industry, altering the ways in which people access information. Corresponding to traditional media, new digital media based on digital technology redefine the spatiotemporal scope and subjects of cultural dissemination, thus becoming a vital medium for transmitting traditional Kazakh culture in the new era.

In the realm of digital transformation, the initiatives of the Kazakhstani government play a pivotal role. According to data from the Eurasian Development Bank's Integration Research Center, the primary driver of digital transformation in Kazakhstan is the public sector, with the highest Digital Implementation Index (DII) [9]. Presently, the "Digital Kazakhstan" national plan focuses on the digitization of all sectors of the economy and the expansion of information and communication technology infrastructure [10]. This initiative has brought forth new opportunities for development and a competitive environment in the media and communication sectors.

In Kazakhstan, many domestic enterprises have actively begun engaging in the process of digital transformation (DT) [11].

With the rapid increase in global internet users, audiences from various sectors such as film, newspapers, news, and entertainment are migrating to digital media platforms. Media technology has altered the media consumption behavior of modern Kazakhstani people, shaping new cultural exchanges, influencing their cultural identities, and continuously shaping and impacting cross-cultural communication patterns.

Through digital transformation, significant changes have occurred in the competitive relationship between traditional and emerging media. Although traditional media still play a crucial role in information dissemination, the rise of new media forms has begun to exert influence on them. In Kazakhstan, while traditional media such as television, newspapers, and radio still dominate the main channels, emerging media forms such as internet websites, social networks, and instant messaging tools are gradually eroding their market share [11]. This indicates that the impact of digital transformation on the media industry extends beyond the technological level and also involves changes in market competition and user behavior.

With the proliferation and convenience of digital media, an increasing number of individuals opt to acquire information through online news platforms. These digital news platforms serve not only as disseminators of news but also as propagators and promoters of cultural information. Through digital news platforms, Kazakhstan's indigenous culture can be showcased to global audiences in a more intuitive and enriched manner, thereby enhancing the dissemination power and influence of indigenous culture.

Furthermore, the proliferation and development of digital media have made the expression of indigenous culture more diverse and personalized. Traditional media forms are constrained by factors such as layout, duration, and time slots, imposing certain limitations on the expression of indigenous culture. However, on digital media platforms, cultural expression can be more freely conducted, unrestricted by time and space. From textual reporting to multimedia formats such as images, videos, and audio, the presentation of indigenous culture becomes more vivid and multidimensional, attracting greater audience attention and enhancing the effectiveness of cultural dissemination.

Moreover, the interactivity and engagement of digital media have brought new opportunities for the dissemination of indigenous culture. In the era of traditional media, audiences could only passively receive information, whereas in the digital media era, audiences can interact with content through commenting, sharing, liking, and even participating in the creation and dissemination of cultural content. This interactivity and participation not only enhance the audience's sense of identity and belonging to indigenous culture but also facilitate the exchange and integration of indigenous culture with global culture.

The Internet big data stands as one of the primary technologies utilized in new digital media. Through the development and application of digital technology, traditional culture emerges more frequently within the public's view. Leveraging its immense computational power and cloud computing platforms, big data technology can store vast amounts of information about traditional culture, thereby facilitating the continuous extension of the value chain of Kazakh indigenous culture.

Cultural dissemination can leverage emerging media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, Facebook, and others. These types of digital media platforms serve as vehicles for recording traditional culture, driving the inheritance and dissemination of Kazakh traditional culture. Additionally, big data algorithms can deliver targeted information to users, greatly enhancing the breadth and efficiency of traditional culture dissemination. Digital media endows the process of traditional cultural dissemination with data thinking, thereby achieving effective communication outcomes. Digital technology enables the rapid dissemination and popularization of core concepts of Kazakh traditional culture to audiences in a short period, significantly boosting the speed of cultural dissemination.

In contemporary society, for instance, short videos are increasingly becoming a part of public life. Integrating the essence of traditional culture into short videos can swiftly pique audience interest within seconds, while also disseminating relevant knowledge of traditional culture in fragmentary form. Leveraging internet technology to aid in the dissemination of traditional culture can render its relatively complex core more directly and comprehensively understood and absorbed by people.

In Kazakhstan's digital media landscape, digital entertainment content holds a significant position, offering audiences a diverse range of entertainment options. From online games and video sharing platforms to streaming services, the richness and diversity of digital entertainment content provide Kazakhstani audiences with more choices and also offer new avenues for the dissemination of indigenous culture. Through digital entertainment content, Kazakhstani bloggers can disseminate indigenous culture to audiences in a more relaxed and engaging manner. Videos can feature Kazakh traditional cultural themes or symbols, enhancing the audience's sense of identity and belonging to indigenous culture.

Digital media art, utilizing digital technology and digital tools as its primary means of creation, spans various domains including computer graphics, digital imaging, digital sculpture, and virtual reality art. In contrast, traditional art places greater emphasis on manual craftsmanship and handiwork. The dissemination of Kazakh culture through digital media art manifests primarily at the technical level, predominantly through means such as mobile short videos. Through these mediums, individuals share and disseminate symbols and symbols related to indigenous culture, such as videos centered around specific traditional cultural themes like the Kazakh traditional festival Nauryz, traditional arts, the Kazakh language, and more. In this manner, audiences can rapidly grasp and appreciate the rich and diverse traditional culture of Kazakhstan within a short span of time. Additionally, some unique traditional cultural documentaries have been produced using digital media art,

transporting audiences to the depths of traditional culture. For instance, documentaries on Kazakh culture such as "Kazakh traditional art of dombra kuy", "Kazakh traditional Assyk games", "Kuresi in Kazakhstan", "Traditional spring festive rites of the Kazakh horse breeders", and "Aitysh/Aitys, art of improvisation" have been released on the YouTube channel "UNESCO". Similarly, videos introducing Kazakh traditional culture have been aired on various channels of Kazakhstani television networks, such as "Jibek Joly TV", which covers all themes of Kazakh culture, including "Kazakh jewelry", "Kazakh national costumes", "Kazakh national game", "Kazakh cuisine - kurt/Kuurdak/", "Kazakh yurt", "Kazakh horse-breeding culture", "Kazakh Marriage", "Kazakh traditional songs", and more. Through digital media, these contents are widely disseminated, injecting new vitality and influence into the dissemination of traditional culture in Kazakhstan.

Education and training in digital media provide opportunities for both those interested in intangible cultural heritage and for its inheritors. This includes instruction and training in traditional Kazakh musical instruments like the Dombra and Kobyz, as well as craftsmanship in making these instruments, traditional embroidery art, and folk handicrafts. Through online platforms, virtual classrooms, and e-learning, individuals can easily access knowledge related to intangible cultural heritage, unrestricted by time and space, making it more convenient and flexible. Digital media not only disseminates the skills and knowledge of intangible cultural heritage but also conveys the cultural values and spiritual essence behind it. Furthermore, digital media serves as a platform for communication and training for inheritors of intangible cultural heritage. Through online videos, live streaming, and other formats, inheritors can impart their skills and share experiences with a broader audience interested in intangible cultural heritage, attracting more young people to join as inheritors. Moreover, inheritors can utilize digital media to provide one-on-one remote guidance and training for apprentices, overcoming the limitations of traditional training methods such as time and geography. This digital education and training contribute to the better transmission of skills by inheritors of intangible cultural heritage, fostering the development of future inheritors and ensuring the sustainable development of intangible cultural heritage.

Digital media has provided a broader platform for the dissemination of the Kazakh language, enabling more native and non-native speakers to access and utilize it. Native speakers can propagate the Kazakh language globally through social media, online videos, digital news platforms, etc., while also attracting more non-native speakers to learn Kazakh. Through online language resources, language learning applications, etc., non-native speakers can conveniently learn and use standardized Kazakh, thereby enhancing the language's usage. Digital media plays a crucial role in the dissemination of the Kazakh language, serving as a vehicle for spreading Kazakhstan's rich cultural content, including its history, traditions, and arts. Therefore, digital media actively facilitates the dissemination of the Kazakh language, contributing to its preservation and development, while also providing an important platform and channel for the dissemination and exchange of local culture.

In the extensive application of digital media, indigenous values are also reflected and emphasized. Digital media platforms serve not only as tools for cultural dissemination but also as channels for conveying and promoting indigenous values. Within Kazakhstan's digital media landscape, many contents underscore indigenous values. For instance, videos introducing Kazakh customs highlight the Kazakh people's emphasis on hospitality, respect for elders and the young, and the primacy of family, reflecting core values cherished and passed down through generations. These values are not only integral to Kazakh society but also guiding principles for the lives and behaviors of its people. Furthermore, these videos provide the younger generation with opportunities to learn and perpetuate traditional values, fostering the continuity and development of indigenous values. This mode of expression also offers global audiences a new pathway to understand the Kazakh culture.

Conclusion

The integration of digital media into various aspects of Kazakh culture has brought about significant transformations and opportunities. From the dissemination of traditional cultural heritage to the promotion of indigenous values, digital media platforms have become invaluable tools in preserving, enriching, and sharing Kazakh culture with the world. In essence, the advent of digital media has ushered in a new era of cultural dissemination and appreciation in Kazakhstan. By harnessing the power of technology, the country has embraced innovative approaches to preserving its rich cultural heritage while embracing the opportunities for global engagement and understanding. As digital media continues to evolve, it will undoubtedly play an increasingly vital role in shaping the cultural landscape of Kazakhstan and fostering cultural dialogue on the global stage.

Literature

1. J. Scott Brennen, Daniel Kreiss. Digitalization. - The International Encyclopedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy, 2016.
2. Kaliev T., Ashimkhanova D., Mussatayeva F. Social Distance of Ethnic Groups: from Proximity to Remoteness (in the Example of Kazakhstan). - Journal of Central Asian Studies, №1 (93), 2024. P. 57-68.
3. Zatonskaya T. Digital Age Media Transformations in Kazakhstan. - Knowledge in the Information Society, Vol. 184, 2021. P. 367–383.
4. Nugumanova K., Kagazbaeva E., Shynar Seitnur. Digital Media as a Factor of Information Security in Kazakhstan. - Qogam jane Daur, №79 (3), 2023. P. 75-90.
5. Nurtayeva D., Kredina A., Kireyeva A., Satybaldin A., Ainakul N. The role of digital technologies in higher education institutions: The case of Kazakhstan. - Problems and Perspectives in Management, Vol. 22, Issue 1, 2024. P. 562-577.
6. Barlybayeva S. Creativity and Media Culture in Modern Kazakhstan. - Technology, Innovation and Creativity in Digital Society, Vol. 345, 2021. P. 352–364.
7. Temirbayeva A.A., Temirbayev T., Ryskiyeva A.A., Kuranbek A.A. The digital palette of Kazakhstan in the context of the study Tengrian internet communities.

- Bulletin of the Karaganda university: "History. Philosophy" series, №1 (109) 2023. P. 323-331.

8. Barlybayeva S., Myssayeva K.N. The new social-cultural order and new media in Kazakhstan. -Al-Farabi Kazakh National University: Herald of journalism, №2 (52), 2019. P. 99-103.

9. Digital Potential of EDB Member Countries, Center for Integration Research / 06/2019, - p. 12
https://eabr.org/upload/iblock/551/EABR_Digital_Potential_06_2019.pdf /

10. State Program — Digital Kazakhstan.// https://digitalkz.kz/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Digital-Kaz_ru.pdf

11. Sultanbayeva G., Lozhnikova O. Digital Transformation in the Kazakhstan. - Kazakh National Pedagogical University named after Abai: bulletin of "Philology" series, №1 (75), 2021. P. 405-414.